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ID ORCID 0000-0002-6583-508X

Associate Professor Fuat Akdenizli

Dokuz Eylül University

THE ROLE OF STATE UNIVERSITIES IN GRAPHIC DESIGN EDUCATION IN TURKEY

Fuat Akdenizli. The Role of State Universities in Graphic Design Education in Turkey. Graphic design education is provided in state universities, private universities and vocational schools in Turkey. Even though private universities have begun to appear in the field of education in recent years, educational quality of state universities is still dominant. In this study, information about graphic design education in Turkey and the importance of state universities in graphic design education are given. Historical development of graphic design departments of state universities in Turkey is chronologically described. Their role in education is explained and compared with private universities. Today, many influential graphic designers in Turkey have graduated from these universities. As a result, it is seen that state universities in Turkey are still the most preferred institutions by students despite the lack of their technology. The current results are important because all of them demonstrate the role of state universities in graphic design education. These results also show that designers who graduated from these universities determine general trends in contemporary Turkish graphic design.

Keywords: *Graphic Design, Graphic Designer, Design, Education, Turkey.*

Фуат Акденізлі. Роль державних університетів у підготовці графічних дизайнерів у Туреччині. Освіту графічного дизайнера можна отримати в державних університетах, приватних університетах та професійних школах Туреччини. Незважаючи на те, що приватні університети почали швидко з'являтися останніми роками, якість освіти державних університетів усе ще домінує. У дослідженні надано інформацію про освіту в галузі графічного дизайну в Туреччині та підкреслюється важливість державних університетів при отриманні освіти графічного дизайнера. Хронологічно описано історичний розвиток кафедр графічного дизайну державних університетів Туреччини. Пояснюється їх роль в освіті, і подається порівняння з приватними університетами. На сьогодні багато впливових графічних дизайнерів у Туреччині закінчили ці університети. Виявлено, що державні університети в Туреччині, як і раніше, є

найбільш привабливими установами, незважаючи на відсутність сучасних технологій. Поточні результати є важливими, оскільки вони демонструють роль державних університетів у галузі графічного дизайну. Даний аналіз підтверджує, що дизайнери, які закінчили ці університети, визначають загальні тенденції сучасного турецького графічного дизайну.

Ключові слова: *графічний дизайн, графічний дизайнер, дизайн, освіта, Туреччина.*

Фуат Акденізлі. Роль государственных университетов в подготовке графических дизайнеров в Турции. Образование графического дизайнера можно получить в государственных университетах, частных университетах и профессиональных школах Турции. Несмотря на то, что частные университеты начали стремительно появляться в последние годы, качество образования государственных университетов все еще доминирует. В данном исследовании представлена информация об образовании в области графического дизайна в Турции и подчеркивается важность государственных университетов при получении образования графического дизайнера. Хронологически описано историческое развитие кафедр графического дизайна государственных университетов Турции. Объяснена их роль в образовании, подается сравнение с частными университетами. На сегодня многие влиятельные графические дизайнеры в Турции окончили эти университеты. Выявлено, что государственные университеты в Турции, как и ранее, являются наиболее привлекательными учреждениями, несмотря на отсутствие современных технологий. Текущие результаты важны, поскольку они демонстрируют роль государственных университетов в области графического дизайна. Данный анализ подтверждает, что дизайнеры, окончившие эти университеты, определяют общие тенденции современного турецкого графического дизайна.

Ключевые слова: *графический дизайн, графический дизайнер, дизайн, образование, Турция.*

Background. Graphic design education is provided by vocational high schools, state universities and private universities in Turkey. Students graduated from graphic departments of vocational high schools receive extra points at entrance examinations of graphic design departments of state universities. Graduates of graphic programs of vocational schools, which provide 2 years of education can continue their study at graphic design departments of universities after they have succeeded in required exams or begin to work professionally. Those students who graduate from these universities after 4 years of studies can attend master and doctoral degree programmes to become academicians. Graphic design education is not only offered in fine arts faculties but also in education faculties. But graduates of education faculties become teachers, not graphic designers.

The purpose of the article is to consider contribution of state universities in contemporary Turkish

graphic design education, to distinguish and characterize graphic design education at state universities and private educational establishments in historical perspective and also in modern context.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The fine arts education appeared in Istanbul where was the capital of the Ottoman Empire before Turkish Republic. In 1883, under the leadership of famous Turkish painter and archaeologist Osman Hamdi Bey, the arts education started under the name of *Sanayi-i Nefise Mektebi*. [7, p. 22] This institution, which will be transformed into *Mimar Sinan University* in the future, has only three departments but graphic design education was not given at that time.

In 1923, with the publicity of the republic, graphic design education became more academic. For the first time in 1927 a “Poster Workshop” was established in Mimar Sinan University. This workshop changed its name to “Graphic Workshop” in 1965 and started to provide more contemporary graphic education. [6, p. 37] This department was renamed in 1979 and in 1982. Today it is known as the Department of Graphic Design. This department specializes mainly in the field of multimedia design and advertising graphics. [6, p. 39]

Another important graphic education institution established in Istanbul is *Marmara University, Fine Arts Faculty, Graphic Department*. This university was founded on January 16, 1883 but graphic design education began in 1957. [4] This department has been established with an approach that emphasizes practice and has attempted to apply principles of “Bauhaus School” in its educational program. [8, p. 58] Since 1982, this department has been continuing to offer a four-year undergraduate program.

Gazi University was founded in Ankara, the capital of the Republic of Turkey is another important educational institution. Gazi University was founded in 1926 and only teachers were trained until 2005. The university has been training graphic designers since 2005 when its fine arts faculty was established. [3] Another important educational institution in Ankara is *Hacettepe University*. On March 28, 1983, the Graphic Department was established under the Faculty of Fine Arts. This Graphic Section has identified the purpose of education in synthesizing national cultural values with a contemporary interpretation. [5]

Izmir is Turkey’s third largest city. Since 1983, the Faculty of Fine Arts in *Dokuz Eylül University* has been providing qualified graphic design education. [2]

Graphic design departments have also increased due to the increase in the number of state universities. Today in Turkey there are 112 state universities and 62 private universities [9] and many of them have Department of Graphic Design in Fine Art Faculty.

Founded in 1984 in Ankara *Bilkent University* is the first private university in Turkey. Then, *Başkent University* was established in Ankara in 1994 and *Yeditepe University* in Istanbul in 1996. [1, p. 72] Many of them have Fine Arts Faculties and Graphic Design Departments. In recent years, Visual Communication Design Departments have been established under the Faculties of Communication. These departments also provide graphic design education. If you look at the curriculum, it is seen that these institutions concentrate on motion graphics and editing rather than desktop publishing. In this context, their graphic design education programmes are controversy.

Graphic design education at all departments in Turkey lasts for 4 years. In the first year of education, Basic Design programme is dominant. In the second year of training in many universities, students are introduced to the field of graphic design such as Graphic Design Studio, Printmaking, etc. In the third year of educational program, which is slightly differs from institution to institution, basic lessons of graphic design field include typography, desktop publishing, illustration, advertisement graphic etc. Graduate students take such specialized courses of graphic design as web design, animation and prepare their final project. In the last two years, there is a wide list of selective courses where students can also take courses from different departments.

A student graduated from the Department of Graphic Design can work as a graphic designer and art director in advertising agencies, government and promotion units of various companies. Students who completed their graduate school and doctoral programme can be academicians after passing necessary exams.

State universities and private universities have some dramatic differences in terms of graphic design education. The list is presented below:

1. The complexity and slowness of procurement processes in government agencies make technology follow-up difficult. At the private university, the purchasing process is done very fast, so it is easier for graphic design students to follow new technologies.

2. Education at state universities is free. Education at private universities has a fee, and this fee may increase over the year by year.

3. In state universities, Special Ability Examinations for selecting students to graphic design departments are more difficult. It is expected that students will have more than one exam to succeed. Special Ability Examinations are not the only determinant because private universities offer paid education.

4. The academic promotion of staff in state universities depends more on the procedure. Private universities distribute their staffs themselves. In this

Fig. 1. Mimar Sinan University in Istanbul

Fig. 2. Dokuz Eylül University Faculty of Fine Arts

Fig.3. Dokuz Eylül University Faculty of Fine Arts Department of Graphic Design

Fig.4. A studio of Department of Graphic Design in Hacettepe University

Fig.5. Special Ability Examinations in Istanbul

Fig. 6. 22nd International Grafist event in Mimar Sinan University in Istanbul Photo:Sinem Üçgül

Fig. 7. A Turkish graphic design student in the Illustration lesson

context, it takes more time to promotion as an academician in state universities.

5. The quotas for graduate and doctoral students in graphic design programs in state universities are limited. It is difficult to win these quotas and students are expected to conduct qualified scientific researches. Private universities usually have no quota limit.

Conclusions. In Turkey graphic design education in state universities is still preferred by students more than private universities. The first reason is educational benefit of established universities. Some of today's successful designers graduated from these universities and established universities and employers accept them as references.

State universities choose from the most talented candidates. It is the fact that more qualified candidates positively affect the quality of education.

In spite of old technological equipment, important national and international graphic design activities are held by state universities. These events also make it easier for graphic design students to interact with the world.

The fact that candidate students do not pay fees to state universities is another reason. Special scholarships are available in private universities but it is difficult to win these scholarships.

If you apply for a job graduation certificates from graphic design departments of state universities still provide a significant advantage in the labour market. Employers prefer students who have graduated from well-established universities.

Students graduated from state universities are advantageous at labour market and they are trendsetters of contemporary Turkish graphic design. Communication between alumnies, professional organizations established by graduates and employers directly affect graphic design trends in Turkey. Today, many graphic designers who have an effect on Turkish graphic design are graduated from state universities. In this context, it is possible to say that state universities in Turkey are the guiding institutions of Turkish graphic design trends.

Bibliography:

1. Ertep H. Kimliğini Arayan Bölüm: Görsel İletişim Tasarımı [Text] / Hakan Ertep // Grafik Tasarım Görsel İletişim Kültürü Dergisi. — 2007. — Sayı:9. — S. 72–77.
2. Grafik [Electronic resource] // Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi — Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi : [official site]. — [2013–2018]. — Access to the resource : <http://gsf.deu.edu.tr/tr/grafik/> (viewed 2018, January 9). — Title from the screen.
3. Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi : Hakkında [Electronic resource] // Güzel Üniversitesi : [official site]. — [20??–2018]. — Access to the resource : <http://gsf.gazi.edu.tr/posts/view/title/hakkinda-130403?siteUri=gsf> (viewed 2018, January 9). — Title from the screen.
4. Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi : Tarihçe [Electronic resource] // Marmara Üniversitesi [official site]. — [2007–2018]. — Access to the resource : <http://gsf.marmara.edu.tr/fakulte/tarihce/> (viewed 2018, January 9). — Title from the screen.
5. Hacettepe Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi : Tarihçe [Electronic resource] // Hacettepe Üniversitesi [official site]. — Access to the resource : http://www.gsf.hacettepe.edu.tr/?page_id=7&lang=tr (viewed 2018, January 9). — Title from the screen.
6. İzer A. Grafik Tasarım Eğitiminde 80 Yıl [Text] / Ayşegül İzer // Grafik Tasarım Görsel İletişim Kültürü Dergisi. — 1998. — Sayı:15. — S. 36–45.
7. Özsezgin K. Çağdaş Sanatımızda Son Osmanlı Osman Hamdi. No:718 [Text] / Kaya Özsezgin. — İstanbul : Kaynak Yayınları, 2015. — 64 s.
8. Temel S. Bauhaus Okulu'ndan Tatbiki Güzel Sanatlar Yüksekokulu'na [Text] / Sema Ilgaz Temel // Grafik Tasarım Görsel İletişim Kültürü Dergisi. — 2008. — Sayı:16. — S. 52–61.
9. Yükseköğretim Bilgi Yönetim Sistemi [Electronic resource] : [Web site]. — Access to the resource : <https://istatistik.yok.gov.tr> (viewed 2018, January 9). — Title from the screen.

References:

1. Ertep, H. (2007). Kimliğini Arayan Bölüm: Görsel İletişim Tasarımı. *Grafik Tasarım Görsel İletişim Kültürü Dergisi*, 9, 72–77. (In Turkish).
2. Grafik. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi — Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi* (2013–2018). Retrieved from <http://gsf.deu.edu.tr/tr/grafik/>. (In Turkish).
3. Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi : Hakkında. *Güzel Üniversitesi*. (20??–2018). Retrieved from <http://gsf.gazi.edu.tr/posts/view/title/hakkinda-130403?siteUri=gsf>. (In Turkish).
4. Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi : Tarihçe. *Marmara Üniversitesi*. (2007–2018). Retrieved from <http://gsf.marmara.edu.tr/fakulte/tarihce/>. (In Turkish).
5. Hacettepe Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi : Tarihçe. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi*. (N. d.). Retrieved from http://www.gsf.hacettepe.edu.tr/?page_id=7&lang=tr. (In Turkish).
6. İzer, A. (1998) Grafik Tasarım Eğitiminde 80 Yıl. *Grafik Tasarım Görsel İletişim Kültürü Dergisi*, 15, 36–45. (In Turkish).
7. Özsezgin, K. (2015). *Çağdaş Sanatımızda Son Osmanlı Osman Hamdi*. (No:718). İstanbul : Kaynak Yayınları, 2015. (In Turkish).
8. Temel, S. (2008). Bauhaus Okulu'ndan Tatbiki Güzel Sanatlar Yüksekokulu'na. *Grafik Tasarım Görsel İletişim Kültürü Dergisi*, 16, 52–61. (In Turkish).
9. *Yükseköğretim Bilgi Yönetim Sistemi* [N. d.]. Retrieved from <https://istatistik.yok.gov.tr>. (In Turkish).